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МАДАНИЯТ ВА САЊЪАТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ КУЛЬТУРА И ИСКУССТВО | JOURNAL OF CULTURE AND ART

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BASICS OF CULTURE AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN HUMAN LIFE

ANNOTATION

This article provides information on the basics of cultural studies. Its subject and purpose are explained. The interrelated lands of culture and human life are mentioned.

Keywords: culture, humanity, research, society, intelligence, knowledge, erudition.

ОСНОВЫ КУЛЬТУРЫ И ЕЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ В ЖИЗНИ ЧЕЛОВЕКА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье представлена информация об основах культурологии. Объясняются его предмет и цель. Упомянуты взаимосвязанные области культуры и человеческой жизни.

Ключевые слова: культура, человечество, исследование, общество, интеллект, знания, эрудиция.

MADANIYAT ASOSLARI VA UNING INSON HAYOTIDAGI AHAMIYATI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada Madaniyatshunoslik asoslari haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Uning mavzusi va maqsadi tushuntiriladi. Madaniyat va inson hayotining o'zaro bog'liq erlari haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniyat, insoniyat, tadqiqot, jamiyat, aql, bilim, bilim.

Cultural studies - studies the most general laws of the development of culture. Its source is all the cultural values that humanity has created. The main task of culturology is to study the joint activities of a person with nature, society, as well as all processes related to the spiritual marriage of people. As a source of his research:

- man-made art space;
- language that is the means of treatment of people;
- knowledge that is the wealth and criterion of society;

- social relations and social organizations; demographic and ethnic processes taking place in society serve. Cultural science is considered a universal science, the characteristic of which is the approach of the phenomenon of a person's cultural life into an orderly system. Culture is also an extremely complex object of knowledge, along with its manifestation in the embodiment of humanitarian knowledge. Culture is not only a set of material and spiritual resources created by the creative activity of people, but at the same time it also represents the level of development of society, that is, the sum of knowledge, criteria and values in society is embodied in culture. In the study of culture, it is also possible not to use objective laws, traditional perceptions of causal dependence in phenomena.

As a general field, a systematic approach to culture provides the opportunity to comprehend the specifics of the different cultural spheres that affect each other in parts, and not in a holistic picture of them. The systematic approach makes it possible to use a huge number of methods of research. That is, the basis is to draw conclusions without contrasting and absolutizing the results obtained with some methods with others. In the history of Culture, various directions-science, technology, education, domestic life, social views, literature, etc. - are studied in a complex way: culture is divided into 2:

1. Material culture;
2. Spiritual culture;

Culture is the level of development of society at a certain historical stage. Expressed in the form of Organization of human life and activities, the material and spiritual values created by humans and the cultural assets created by mankind remain not only the assets left by the people of the past, but also a mirror that reflects the thoughts and thoughts of human intelligence, life. It is the systematic approach that allows people to also understand the spheres of life activity, reacting to culture in its own form. From these, fields of culture, institutions of culture are formed, which, having a clear structure and clear tasks, determine the system of culture, organizing the principle of social relations, communication, cultural patterns.

There are the following departments of cultural studies:

1. *Philosophy of culture* - based on comparative analysis, classification, demonstrating the most general principles of the approach in the analysis of complex and multifaceted processes in culture. There are materialistic, positivistic, objective idealistic and many other views associated with philosophical understanding of culture, philosophical justification. In each of them, methods and specific analytical methods of theoretical explanation of the formation and development of the activities of physical, spiritual and mental life in the world of nature and social group (socium) of a person are developed.

2. *The structural form (morphology) of a culture* - a specific form of a culture that does not depend on a person and exists independently in society-is the subject of his research. Believing that the development of culture is interdependent on the internal laws of society, the morphology of Culture attempts to reveal the source and factors of the development of Culture on the basis of comparison, analysis and other methods. The period of its existence is from the emergence to the crisis of this or that culture.

3. *Sociology of culture* - deals with the study of the exact processes of the existing culture in any society; it is manifested in the interaction of people in the context of a given culture, in the categories of sociomadanity, in the Empric (experimental) study of the cultural process, which is associated with the collection, processing and analysis of various sociological information.

4. *Cultural history* - explores each culture as a unique and original phenomenon; it also compares different cultures, explores their relationships and interactions, their differences in time and space, and the specific and common aspects in their cultural progress.

5. *Ecology of culture* - modern man covers all spheres of life activity: the individual life of a person, the life of society, his interaction with nature. It is one of the newest actively developing fields in cultural studies.

The main problem of cultural science is considered to be Man, zero culture is what man has created. Culturology studies the active relationship of a person with the universe and the manifestation of this relationship in his way of life, the social and cultural role of the individual, the typology of cultures. The science of cultural studies scientifically interprets culture, determines its universal content and meaning, justifies its place and position in the system of socio-historical knowledge. The term "culture" is expressed in colorful meanings in modern scientific literature. The terms "culture" and "culture", according to experts, came from the Latin meaning "processing", "care". It was later used in the context of "being enlightened", "disciplined", "being educated". The term "culture", widely used in Uzbek, means "cultural"-"urban" in Arabic.

If American cultural scientists A. Kreber and K. Klalkxon's. According to the 1952 data of the clachons, the definition given to the phenomenon of culture is 164, while in recent literature this number is more than 400. There are many explanations in the description of the phenomenon of culture "the way of living humanity; the full - fledged activity of a social person", "the environment created by man", "a holistic social organism", a set of material and spiritual values created by mankind; artificial-second nature; the product of human creative activity; society in general; the spiritual state of society; the quality of society. Although the concept of culture in Western Europe acquired its present meaning from the late 18th century, it was not until the 20th century that it gained a solid place from the categorical system of Social Sciences and humanities. The need for generalizing concepts, which have an incomparable scope of personality society and contribute to a certain regulation of constantly changing information, has caused the concept of culture to become widespread. In ancient Rome, the concept of "Culture" was also used to mean "care for the spiritual improvement and purification of life."

According to reports, the famous Roman philosopher-speaker Ciceron also used the term "culture of the soul". In European peoples until the late 18th century, the term "culture" was used side by side with the concept of mental-moral culture. It turns out that the concept of "Culture" has not changed its essence from ancient times to the present, despite its diverse interpretation. The scientific concept of culture in the present era was born as a result of the awareness of the uniqueness of spirituality, the psyche, which is created and continues to be created by mankind. The birth of the idea of culture is controversial during the period when humanity lived on the basis of a "natural" lifestyle, that is, when they were engaged in picking, hunting, fishing, livestock and farming. In a simple, unambiguously developing society, a person lived "merged" with his culture. Customs, beliefs, material and social forms of life did not differ from him. The manifestation of the autonomy of culture requires to some extent the development of techniques and the achievement of socialization of Labor. On this basis, culture gradually becomes more and more independent of humanity. And the subordination of a person to his culture increases. The existing problems in the environmental, spiritual and moral spheres in current post-industrial societies are evidence of our opinion.

Therefore, it becomes necessary to perceive culture as a phenomenon, understand the laws of its development and learn to control culture on the basis of these concepts. Human society is in constant development, it is changing and improving. In different historical periods and in different cultures, people perceive and perceive the world in their own way, generating their imagination and knowledge in their own way. We turn to the past with questions by learning how people have overcome the obstacles that are similar to existing problems in the present, the past answers us, and thus there is a constant dialogue between the past, the present and the future.

Culture is the product of society, one of the most important aspects of social life. Just as there is no society without culture, culture does not exist outside of society. A distinctive feature of culture as a complex social reality is that it absorbs, preserves and constantly enriches the work and knowledge of human generations. Culture represents the areas of social life that have to do with the succession, the accumulation of values and the delivery of them to the next generations. The role of culture as a component of social life in society depends on the content of society and the characteristics of the social being being analyzed.

The social process, the behavior of people, that is, social activity, also acts as a tool in the decision-making or elimination of cultural ideals, values, norms, as well as a form of interpersonal and Intergroup Relations of people's social and personal relationships. Culture is expressed in the structural and functional aspects of social life. In this respect, society gives rise to culture. The more complex and rich the culture that has arisen in society, the more perfect its influence on man and society, the more its relative independence increases. For example, while antique society has already become a past, a history, its culture continues to hold its importance in the present, or we know more of the culture of this period than it did at that time.

Therefore, although culture is viewed as a product of society, as a style of activity, each society can also be viewed in the form of a source of formation of one or another concrete culture. Social progress leads to changes in the interaction of activity and culture. While informational activity in traditional and industrial societies formed an independent sphere, in the conditions of the "computer revolution", the production of information, knowledge, the creation of new technologies were formed as a separate type of activity, information became a valuable commodity. Complex changes in the system of synthesis of knowledge in informational activity affect ideas and values for which an important decision is made. As a result of the accumulation of reserves of information of spiritual culture, it became an organizing and moving factor in the development of civilization.

This resulted in changes in the interaction of activity and culture. If initially the culture was fully dependent on the content of the activity, activity is observed to form in the wake of civilizing processes with the growing involvement of the culture. It is also necessary to take into account the great influence of historical inertia in the scourge of society. Under the influence of inertia, humanity is completely obsessed with other things than the tasks that need to be completed. Because team thinking is rebuilt with difficulties.

In general, the concept of intelligibility differs from the very fact that it is defined at the level of scientific and ordinary consciousness. At the normal level of consciousness, intelligentsia refers to educated people with higher education, mainly engaged in mental work. In scientific understanding, intelligibility is interpreted as not dependent on this level of information, knowledge, erudition. Even if a person is deprived of his memory and does not have a higher education-if he retains the ability to understand other people of culture, wide and diverse areas of art and ideas of others, adapts to intellectual life – this is intelligence. That is to say, intelligence is a spiritual state, which, although it is given to some people from nature, but a person achieves it through tireless work and research.

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